

*Fostering the integration of RRI within
regional R&I strategies:
Recommendations from the RRI2SCALE
Project*

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RRI2SCALE

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT REGIONAL SCALE

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RRI2SCALE

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*Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale
for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy*

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PROJECT OVERVIEW	RRI2SCALE has designed a robust methodological approach to assist regional R&I governance systems to effectively and sustainably address their Regional Dilemmas. Techno-moral scenarios will be “tested” via JRC’s Scenario Exploration System and Regional Dialogues, forming the basis for elaborating Regional Agendas and Roadmaps towards the integration of RRI principles into territorial R&I design. All project results will form the RRI2SCALE Toolkit for replication by other territories.
CONSORTIUM/	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA https://www.apre.it/ 2. HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET https://www.hvl.no/ 3. UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/ 4. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE https://www.utwente.nl/en/ 5. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC https://qplan-intl.gr/ 6. RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH https://www.research-and-innovation-management.com/ 7. WHITE RESEARCH SPRL https://white-research.eu/ 8. HORDALAND FYLKESKOMMUNE https://www.hordaland.no/ 9. PROVINCIE OVERIJSEL https://www.overijssel.nl/ 10. KRITI https://www.crete.gov.gr/ 11. AXENCIA GALEGA DE INNOVACION http://gain.xunta.gal/

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Fostering the integration of RRI within regional R&I strategies: Recommendations from the RRI2SCALE Project

Local and regional policy-makers are often called to find a balance between innovation and growth policies, and choices that prioritize inclusiveness, sustainability and citizens' quality of life. These two aspects shall coexist in order to build a desirable and sustainable future.

The RRI2SCALE projects has experimented in this direction, fostering the integration of Responsible Research and Innovation practices and principles within regional research and innovation strategies, including climate adaptation, and engagement activities.

This Policy Brief summarises the main objectives and achievements attained during the RRI2SCALE project. Based on the lessons learnt and deeper reflections on them, it also provides policy recommendations that provide guidance on which high-level governance actions can better strengthen Responsible Research and Innovation in regional procedures, plans and strategies.

SUMMARY OF RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1. Define, translate and implement the RRI concept in relation to territory-specific challenges.**
- 2. Foster awareness about governance innovation in the political culture.**
- 3. Encourage a common vision and value alignment across governance levels and institutional departments.**
- 4. Outline RRI implications on governance processes more explicitly outlined.**
- 5. Create a culture of participatory governance at all levels of society.**
- 6. Provide guidance to make the right choices in terms of stakeholders to be involved.**
- 7. Encourage the use of foresight methodologies as tools to expand awareness and reflection, and to acknowledge unbalances and biases in engagement and communication processes.**

1. The RRI2SCALE experience

Nowadays, local and regional policy-makers across the European Union (EU) are often faced with the challenge of finding a balance between policies aimed at implementing sustainable development and economic growth on one side, and the need to ensure citizens' inclusiveness and quality of life on the other.

Also, the current techno-social landscape requires more 'social', open and collaborative governance models involving substantial cooperation among sectors of government, business, academia and society to upscale institutional capacity for territorial development and transformation as well as secure the sustainability of the introduced policies and measures.

RRI2SCALE wanted to tackling such challenges, defining and carrying into action regional plans and strategies that would drive progress and economic development while also promoting sustainability, inclusiveness, and citizen quality of life. It worked with four regional governmental authorities: Vestland County (Norway), Province Overijssel (Netherlands), Crete (Greece), Galicia (Spain).

RRI2SCALE core objective was to foster the integration and harmonization of actionable Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) values, practices and principles in regional innovation strategies and governance processes, providing methodological guidance and focusing on two main aspects of the RRI model.

- *public engagement* – stressing the importance of including societal partners in decision-making;
- *governance innovation* – adapting towards more responsible, open, collaborative and responsive organisational and governance forms.

RRI2SCALE has implemented a solid methodological approach to support public engagement and governance innovation in regional R&I governance systems, through:

- **Interviews and surveys** with stakeholders;
- **Scouting and monitoring RRI dimensions** – including best practices – at the regional level;
- **Developing techno-moral scenarios** and testing them through the **Scenario Exploration System (SES)** method, to implement **multistakeholder collaborative moral reflection-in-action**;
- **Organising Cross-regional dialogues**, to cross-fertilise our findings, enrich and cluster our results effectively, and promote the development of cross-regional partnerships on territorial RRI;
- **Promoting transformative changes** in our participating regions supporting them in the development of Agendas and Roadmaps to embed actionable RRI values in regional innovation governance processes, and opening the way for a more open, transparent and democratic governance.

2. Policy recommendations

The following policy recommendations have been developed based on the lessons that have been learned during the project and the feedback received during public events. Recommendations intend offering guidance on how Responsible Research and Innovation can be promoted and integrated in regional procedures, plans, and strategies through high-level governance actions and innovations.

They have been developed around three main challenges:

1. RRI definition and narrative,
2. RRI and governance innovation culture,
3. Engagement methodologies and approaches.

2.1 RRI definition and narrative

2.1.1 *Define, translate and implement the RRI concept in relation to territory-specific challenges*

Explaining the essence of a complex and variegated concept such as RRI is not an easy task.

In our discussions, views on RRI varied from region to region, in relation to each specific social and innovation context. We found, however, an overall constant in the request for clarification and in the need to better understand and define how RRI can be applied to the regions' specific playground. This suggested the need to slightly alter the narrative, focusing on terms that are more familiar to the regional context and closer to existing or emerging policies and practices.

The RRI concept shall be defined, translated – and then implemented – in relation to territory-specific challenges, adapting it to different cultural schemes, priorities or criticalities, which are normally cultural and/or time-dependent. This shall be done “unpacking” the concept of RRI, and focusing on its content rather than on the concept itself, creating awareness on the different layers composing the concept:

- **Referring to RRI values and principles:** anticipation, reflexivity, responsiveness, inclusion, transparency, sustainability.
- **Referring to specific policy areas and issues,** using wording and terms that are more familiar to each context-specific innovation ecosystems, policy objectives or need. This may comprise:
 - the official RRI policy areas – gender, equality and inclusivity; ethical issues; science education; openness and public engagement;
 - some more specific and concrete policy level application, e.g.: open data; transparency of procedures; social equality; environmental sustainability; social innovation; participation ladder/participatory decision making. Specific contingent needs – for example unemployment – helped in one region to reflect more concretely on RRI.
- **Referring to more general and holistic objectives** e.g., consensus; wider social benefit to society; general well-being; impact that innovation investments have in society, etc.
- **Creating more awareness** about the governance level.
- **Working on enabling approaches and methods,** such as participatory and co-creation approaches.

2.2 RRI and governance innovation culture

Education and awareness on RRI values and practices, in particular on innovative and participatory governance, is needed at all levels of society, comprising all level of governance as well as citizens. It emerged how much work is still to be done on the acceptance of the need for participation from policy makers and businesses.

2.2.2 *Foster awareness about governance innovation in the political culture*

We cannot count yet on a dominant political culture that can support RRI values and approaches (in particular participation). In a time were democracy and its values are experiencing a crisis, the creation of such a culture is all the more critical.

From our experience, a fundamental obstacle towards this transformation relates to the fact that the pace and priorities linked to political election agendas often clash with the longer time that a proper stakeholder engagement process requires, to enable substantial contributions from citizens and build sustainable relationships. Similarly, power shifts and changes within the governing bodies, following political elections, produce significant impacts on the agenda of regional authorities. This is in conflict with the long-term nature of “discourse change”, at the regional level, towards RRI-informed governance. RRI can become fully integrated into processes only if:

- Training models are developed for civil servants and politicians to raise awareness and give them tools to better include possibilities of responsible innovation at the regional institutional level
- The message, vision and mentality of RRI is conveyed publicly by the higher political level, becoming part of the public political discourse, lexicon, and desirable value system.
- Harmonization will be sought between the time of politics that of engagement processes.

2.2.3 *Encourage a common vision and value alignment across governance levels and institutional departments*

Collaboration across departments is key to achieve and implement institutional change, and shall be strengthened. For example, it was proved crucial to attract and reach out to the right stakeholders, representing all different knowledge areas, sectors, population groups.

However, such cooperation represented an important challenge. In lack of institutionalised procedures, including dedicated budget, the work related to participative process is still perceived and treated by different ministries and departments as an additional burden, extraneous to regular work objectives, agendas, planned time or allocated resources. It is therefore important that:

- **Value alignment and a common vision exists – in the sense of common wishes and a common “language”** – among civil servants and policy makers – as the basis for understanding what governance innovation is, to agree on the need for it, and to find the suitable practical way to make it possible. For instance, which are the **ethical aspects** we all share and would like to be reflected in our vision of the future?
- All stakeholders know clearly about **“what is at stake”**. The **expected “costs” of not implementing the governance innovation should be communicated** to all the decision makers, as this can minimize the potential frictions that might jeopardize the implementation of the new governance strategy.

2.2.4 *Outline RRI implications on governance processes more explicitly outlined*

Identifying how RRI shall be integrated at the governance level – meaning, in which concrete process – was not always easy. In order to ensure a practice truly informed by RRI values in (regional) governance, a codification effort is needed:

- The possible implication of the different RRI dimensions for existing governance processes (existing norms, processes and procedures underpinning the functioning of institutions and society) need to be identified.
- In each process (strategy, plan, procedure) where RRI integration is sought, implications shall be codified in the planning procedure documents as clearly as possible, for example defining clauses on the minimum level of bindingness of those instructions (e.g., on inclusiveness and the target groups, on ethical considerations, on openness for access by all affected entities).
- It is important to acknowledge that small steps also make a difference.
- Securing dedicated financial and human resources to implement RRI processes is an important enabling measure, for example to allow coordination and cooperation across different governance levels and institutional divisions.

In RRI2SCALE we discussed different possibilities of RRI integration at the evaluation level, when designing project funding schemes or public procurement specifications:

- Adding evaluation criteria based on RRI values to the conventional procedure of assessment for the technologically innovative potential of proposals. The so-called Societal Readiness Level (SRL) criterion was added to stimulate the contribution of innovation proposals for societal change.
- Integrating RRI at the process level, adopting a participative approach to design the evaluation procedure, allowing stakeholders to discuss what KPIs are important for each of them.
- Integrate requirements and conditions related to the use of future perspective tools in public procurement procedures.

2.2.5 *Create a culture of participatory governance at all levels of society*

Trust calls for engagement, and engagement creates trust; the greater the trust, the higher the demand for engagement. Our results highlighted that trust indicators (i.e., transparency and trust in regional organizations) significantly drive citizen demands to be engaged in policy making, since they have increased confidence in other partners’ commitment to a greater good. At the same time, active citizen engagement increases trust. Thus, the stronger the correlation between trust and citizen engagement for tackling grand societal challenges, the greater the value for all sides. Participatory governance, trust and demand for engagement, however, are also based on a well-informed citizenship about governance themes, and this can be achieved through formal and informal modes of training. Passive manifestations of trust may backfire in terms of engagement, as blind citizen reliance on institutions may lead citizens to withdraw from deliberation processes in the long term.

- When it comes to future-oriented and anticipatory approaches to governance, early education of citizens (e.g., during high school) would be relevant and fruitful to increase their ability to implement responsible innovation proposal, and to “own” the future plans.
- For a holistic fostering of engagement levels, trust need to be both vertical (i.e., towards institutions) and horizontal (i.e., between stakeholder groups). The RRI2SCALE experience indicates that the overall social capital stock at the ecosystem level is of critical importance to encourage citizens to develop a shared feeling of a common vision for their territory.

2.3 Engagement Methodologies and approaches

All regions face challenges in involving various stakeholders in regional innovation, including disinterest from stakeholders and a focus on short-term effects by policy makers rather than participatory processes. They noted that interactions with citizens are often limited and agree that meaningful engagement, in which citizens' views are included in the decision-making process, is desirable. However, it was emphasized that responsible innovation involves more than just engagement with citizens, reinforcing the importance of encouraging quadruple helix stakeholders, including politicians and citizens, to engage in regional innovation.

This type of meaningful engagement requires proper guidance, to enable a conscious and systematic approach to participation processes, a proper understanding and use of the different levels of participation, and eventually the capacity to outreach to citizens who are generally not involved.

2.3.1 *Provide guidance to make the right choices in terms of stakeholders to be involved*

Involving public voices in a *meaningful* way is hard work. Not all stakeholders need to be always involved, because: they might have been already involved and we know what they think; to avoid overinvolvement of the “usual suspects” and connected biases; because they do not have the needed competence for a certain discussion or phase. Similarly, conscious efforts shall be done to reach out to those who have never been involved; those we do not know how to communicate with; those who are not interested, do not care or do not understand the issue.

Deciding to include, or not to, implies a level of responsibility. Therefore, it is important that any choice comes from a responsible, critical, aware, motivated and conscious act. The capacity to critically distinguish those processes that can be more open and participative from those that are less suitable for wider participative actions, is important and needs to be supported.

- Guidance is needed to make the right choices on whom, why, how, to involve, and at which level of participation.
- When guidance is provided at the national level (e.g., within official planning procedures) it is important to enable a meaningful balance between top-down provisions and bottom-up actions, not to stifle creativity and context-related relevance.

2.3.2 *Encourage the use of foresight methodologies as tools to expand awareness and reflection, and to acknowledge unbalances and biases in engagement and communication processes*

Any communication and engagement process inherently reflects unbalances connected to consolidated power structures, dynamics, relations and roles. It is therefore important to acknowledge and address such unbalances and perspective biases. Some methodologies may be more appropriate to address this challenge. Foresight methodologies, for example, can help addressing issues related to consolidated power relations amongst stakeholders because they:

- Push to adopt a reflexive and anticipatory thinking approach, helping to put into discussion existing paradigms.
- Call for a more diversified arena of stakeholders.

- Help breaking, flattening or rearranging existing consolidated power structures and their inevitable influences on discussions and decision-making, because it allows envisioning different pathways and possibilities. This is because when we develop new reality scenarios, we create situations and realities that are often **not connected to the current dominant discourse and do not descend from the dominant narrative**. Creating new narratives around a subject (including the value systems underpinning such reality) may facilitate or actuate shifts in power distributions across stakeholders.

In RRI2SCALE we experimented in particular three foresight tools:

A tool to understand world and sectoral trends: The Delphi survey

The Delphi method is a multi-round expert survey in which “in the second and later rounds of the survey, the results of the previous round are given as feedback”. It facilitates the development of reliable group opinions by providing experts from various fields with a forum for discussion within a structured setting.

A tool to expand awareness and reflection: techno-moral scenarios

Scenarios, as a particular form or part of foresight activities, proved to stimulate reflections about future systemic implications, and the adoption of an anticipatory approach, increasing consciousness about long-term or wider societal implications of our choices, including understanding soft implications of technologies in the medium/long-run.

A specific engagement tool: Scenario Exploration System (SES)

The SES methodology allows all voices to be heard at the same time in the process, compared to other processes where contributions are sought in silos or sequence. Also, it enables players to think and act out-of-the-box, giving the possibility to play roles and experience dynamics out of their usual social and professional role, and shifting or widening their perspectives. This translates in an increased capacity of understanding the motivations and interests of others.

3. Conclusions

The process of integrating RRI principles into regional development strategies is a complex one. The RRI concept itself is neither commonly shared nor homogeneously understood. The concept adapts into territory-specific challenges and needs to be more deeply shared. Encouraging quadruple helix stakeholders, including politicians and citizens, to engage in regional innovation is key to ensure an efficient process.

This type of meaningful engagement, in which also citizens' views are taken into account in the decision-making process, will require the use of proper participatory tools as well as the progressive building of a shared culture and awareness across all societal levels, on holistic approaches to research and innovation, as well as to governance innovation.